

RELATIVE INFINITE INFORMATION THEORY

Using Mathematics as a tool to describe Information in the Universe.

Is Information Infinite but Relative?

Suppose that this Infinite Integer Numbers dotted line represents information in the entire Universe.

$[-\infty; +\infty]$ = infinite points (information)

But if we take a random segment in this dotted line:

$[0; 500]$ = finite information [500 points (information)]

and random segment in this dotted line:

$[200; 300]$ = finite information [100 points (information)]

and a random segment in this dotted line:

$[220; 250]$ = finite information [30 points (information)]

Conclusion:

The theory uses mathematics as a tool to describe information in the Universe and concludes that information is indeed infinite but relative (not absolute). As the “size” of the interval decreases, so does the number of points (which in this case represent information).

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